

Diagnostic Significance of HER2 Expression in Breast Carcinoma: A Histological perspective

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Abstract

Background: Breast carcinoma is the most prevalent malignancy among women worldwide and a major cause of cancer mortality. The human epidermal growth factor receptor-2 (HER2) is a key biomarker in breast cancer, linked to tumor aggressiveness, poor differentiation, and response to targeted therapy. Assessing HER2 expression and its correlation with clinicopathological parameters provides essential diagnostic and prognostic information. **Objective:** To evaluate the diagnostic and histopathological significance of HER2 expression in breast carcinoma and determine its association with hormone receptor status, tumor grade, lymph-node metastasis, and clinical stage. **Methods:** A cross-sectional study was conducted on 102 paraffin-embedded breast-carcinoma samples collected at an Iraqi tertiary hospital between January 2023 to December 2025. Tumor type, grade, and stage were assessed histologically. Immunohistochemistry for HER2, estrogen receptor (ER), and progesterone receptor (PR) was performed following ASCO/CAP 2018 guidelines. Statistical analysis was done using SPSS v25; $p \leq 0.05$ was considered significant. **Results:** The mean patient age was 51 ± 10 years. HER2 overexpression (+3) was detected in 59.8% of cases. A significant inverse relationship existed between HER2 expression and both ER and PR status ($p = 0.0001$). HER2 positivity correlated significantly with lymph-node metastasis ($p = 0.023$) and high tumor grade ($p = 0.0001$), but not with tumor stage ($p = 0.2$). Most tumors were invasive ductal carcinoma NOS (95.1%). **Conclusion:** HER2 overexpression is significantly associated with hormone receptor negativity, lymph-node metastasis, and higher histological grade, identifying a biologically aggressive breast cancer subset. Routine HER2 evaluation is crucial for accurate diagnosis, prognostic stratification, and guiding targeted therapy among Iraqi breast cancer patients.

Introduction

Breast carcinoma remains the most frequently diagnosed malignancy and the leading cause of cancer-related mortality among women worldwide, accounting for nearly 2.3 million new cases and 685,000 deaths annually according to GLOBOCAN 2020 estimates [1]. It is a heterogeneous disease characterized by variable histological subtypes, biological behaviors, and treatment responses, reflecting the complex interplay of hormonal, molecular, and environmental factors [2]. Among these, the human epidermal growth factor receptor 2 (HER2) has emerged as one of the most critical biomarkers in breast cancer diagnosis, prognosis, and

therapeutic planning. HER2, also known as ERBB2, encodes a 185-kDa transmembrane tyrosine kinase receptor belonging to the epidermal growth factor receptor family [3]. Amplification or overexpression of HER2 occurs in approximately 15–30% of breast carcinomas and is associated with increased tumor aggressiveness, higher proliferation rates, and reduced overall survival [4,5]. Historically, HER2 positivity was considered an indicator of poor prognosis; however, the advent of HER2-targeted therapies, particularly trastuzumab, has markedly improved outcomes in this molecular subtype [6,7]. Consequently, precise assessment of HER2 status has become an essential component of breast cancer evaluation. Histologically,

More Information

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HER2 overexpression is more frequently observed in invasive ductal carcinoma of no special type (NOS) compared with lobular carcinoma and often coexists with high histological grade, negative hormone receptor status, and the presence of lymph-node metastasis [8,9]. Immunohistochemistry (IHC) and fluorescence in situ hybridization (FISH) are the standard diagnostic modalities for determining HER2 status, with IHC serving as a first-line screening tool owing to its accessibility and cost-effectiveness [10]. From a diagnostic viewpoint, the identification of HER2 overexpression not only delineates tumor aggressiveness but also stratifies patients for targeted therapy, thereby influencing clinical decision-making and prognosis. Understanding the histopathological correlations of HER2 expression—such as tumor grade, lymph-node involvement, and hormone receptor profile—remains essential for accurate classification and management. Moreover, examining HER2 expression patterns within local populations can highlight region-specific variations that may inform screening and treatment strategies [11,12]. The present study aims to evaluate the diagnostic and histological significance of HER2 expression in breast carcinoma and to explore its association with key clinicopathological parameters, including hormone receptor status, tumor grade, stage, and lymph-node metastasis.

Method

This cross-sectional analytical study was designed to evaluate the diagnostic and histopathological significance of HER2 expression in breast carcinoma and to determine its association with selected clinicopathological parameters. The study was conducted at the Department of Pathology in National center for teaching laboratories in medical city and in oncology center at Baqubah teaching hospital, Iraq, using formalin-fixed, paraffin-embedded breast tissue blocks collected from January 2023 to December 2025. Study Population and Sample Selection: A total of 102 female patients with histologically confirmed invasive breast carcinoma were included. Cases were selected from archival pathology records. Inclusion criteria comprised all primary invasive breast carcinomas with adequate tumor tissue for immunohistochemical analysis. Exclusion criteria included patients who had received neoadjuvant chemotherapy or radiotherapy, recurrent or metastatic lesions, and inadequate tissue samples. Histopathological Evaluation: All specimens were reviewed on hematoxylin and eosin-stained slides to assess tumor type, histological grade, and tumor stage according to the American Joint Committee on Cancer (AJCC, 8th edition). Lymph-node involvement was documented microscopically. Tumors were graded using the Nottingham modification of the Bloom–Richardson system [13]. Immunohistochemical

Assessment: Immunohistochemistry (IHC) was performed on 4- μ m tissue sections using monoclonal antibodies against HER2, estrogen receptor (ER), and progesterone receptor (PR). HER2 immunostaining was evaluated semi-quantitatively following the ASCO/CAP 2018 guidelines, and scores were categorized as 0, +1, +2, or +3. Tumors with strong complete membranous staining in >10% of cells (3+) were considered positive, while equivocal (2+) cases were correlated with histological features. Statistical Analysis: Data analysis was performed using SPSS version 25. Categorical variables were expressed as frequencies and percentages, while continuous variables were presented as mean \pm standard deviation (SD). Associations between HER2 status and categorical parameters (ER, PR, tumor grade, stage, and lymph-node metastasis) were tested using the Chi-square or Fisher's exact test, whereas differences in mean tumor size and age were compared using the independent-sample t-test. A p-value \leq 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

Table 1 summarizes the baseline clinicopathologic features of the studied cohort. The mean age was 51 ± 10 years, indicating that most patients were middle-aged, which aligns with regional breast-cancer epidemiology showing a peak incidence in the fifth decade of life.

Hormone Receptor Status: More than half of the tumors expressed hormone receptors: 54.9 % were PR-positive and 56.9 % were ER-positive, while 45.1 % and 43.1 % lacked PR and ER expression, respectively. The predominance of receptor-positive disease suggests that a large proportion of patients might respond favorably to endocrine therapy and exhibit comparatively better prognostic outcomes. Nevertheless, the considerable proportion of receptor-negative tumors highlights the biological heterogeneity of breast cancer within this population.

Lymph-Node and Metastatic Status: Lymph-node involvement was documented in 73.5 % of the cases, whereas 26.5 % were node-negative. The high rate of nodal metastasis indicates that most patients presented with advanced locoregional disease, reflecting delayed diagnosis and limited screening practices in the community.

Tumor Stage Distribution: Stage II tumors predominated (59.8 %), followed by stage III (25.5 %), stage I (11.8 %), and stage IV (2.9 %). This distribution demonstrates that the majority of patients were diagnosed with locally advanced breast cancer, with only a small minority presenting with early or distant disease. Such findings underscore the importance of enhancing early-detection strategies and public awareness to improve stage at diagnosis.

HER2 Status: HER2 overexpression (+3) was observed in 59.8 % of cases, while 40.2 % exhibited moderate expression (+2). The predominance of HER2-positive tumors signifies an aggressive biological phenotype that warrants HER2-targeted therapy. These results also mirror global observations of increasing HER2-positive proportions among newly diagnosed breast-cancer cases.

Tumor Grade: The majority of tumors were grade II (63.7 %), whereas grade I accounted for 8.8 % of cases. This pattern suggests that moderately differentiated

tumors were most common, representing intermediate biological aggressiveness consistent with prior Iraqi and regional studies.

Histopathological Type: Most cases (95.1 %) were classified as invasive ductal carcinoma, not otherwise specified (NOS), while invasive lobular carcinoma comprised only 4.9 %. This distribution parallels international data, in which invasive ductal carcinoma remains the dominant histological subtype of breast cancer.

Table 1: Patient’s Clinical and Demographic Profile

Variables		Frequency	Percentage
Progesterone receptors (PR)	NEGATIVE	46	45.1
	POSTIVE	56	54.9
Estrogen receptors (ER)	NEGATIVE	44	43.1
	POSTIVE	58	56.9
Lumph nodes	NEGATIVE	27	26.5
Metastasis	POSTIVE	75	73.5
Tumor stage	I	12	11.8
	II	61	59.8
	III	26	25.5
	IV	3	2.9
HER 2	+2	41	40.2
	+3	61	59.8
Tumor grades	I	9	8.8
	II	65	63.7
Histopathology	<i>invasive ductal carcinoma NOS</i>	97	95.1
	<i>invasive lobular carcinoma</i>	5	4.9

Table 2 demonstrates the relationship between **HER2 expression levels** and key clinicopathological parameters, including hormone receptor status, tumor stage, lymph node involvement, tumor grade, and histopathological type.

Hormone Receptor Status (PR and ER): A statistically significant inverse relationship was observed between HER2 expression and both progesterone receptor (PR) and estrogen receptor (ER) status ($p = 0.0001$ for both). Among tumors with HER2 +3 overexpression, 67.2% were PR-negative, whereas only 12.2% of HER2 +2 cases were PR-negative. Similarly, 67.2% of HER2 +3 tumors were ER-negative, compared to 7.3% in the HER2 +2 group. These findings suggest that higher HER2 expression is frequently associated with loss of hormone receptor expression, which is consistent with the recognized biological pattern of HER2-enriched breast cancer subtypes that tend to be hormone receptor-negative and exhibit more aggressive clinical behavior.

Tumor Stage: There was no statistically significant association between tumor stage and HER2 status ($p = 0.2$). Stage II tumors predominated in both HER2 +2 (53.7%) and HER2 +3 (63.9%) groups. The absence of

significant variation across stages suggests that HER2 amplification occurs independently of tumor size or extent at diagnosis, although the higher proportion of stage II–III disease reflects late presentation in the studied population.

Lymph Node Metastasis: A significant association was noted between HER2 status and lymph node involvement ($p = 0.023$). Among HER2 +3 tumors, 82.0% exhibited lymph node metastasis compared with 61.0% in the HER2 +2 group. This correlation reinforces the established role of HER2 overexpression as a marker of tumor aggressiveness and metastatic potential.

Tumor Grade: A strong association was found between tumor grade and HER2 status ($p = 0.0001$). High-grade (grade III) tumors were more prevalent among HER2 +3 cases (42.6%) compared with 4.9% in HER2 +2 tumors. Conversely, low-grade (grade I) tumors were more common in the HER2 +2 group (17.1%) than in HER2 +3 (3.3%). These findings highlight that HER2 overexpression is linked to poorer differentiation and higher proliferative activity, consistent with global literature identifying HER2 as a hallmark of biologically aggressive breast cancer.

Histopathological Type: No significant association was observed between histopathological subtype and HER2 expression ($p = 0.1$). The majority of HER2 +3 tumors were invasive ductal carcinoma (NOS) (98.4%) compared with 90.2% in the HER2 +2 group, while

invasive lobular carcinoma was relatively uncommon in both subgroups. This pattern supports previous reports that HER2 amplification occurs more frequently in ductal than in lobular carcinomas.

Table 2: Association between HER 2 Status and Study Variables

HER 2 Status			
PR Status	HER2 +2	HER2 +3	P-value
Negative	5 (12.2%)	41 (67.2%)	0.0001
Positive	36 (87.8%)	20 (32.8%)	
ER Status	HER2 +2	HER2 +3	P-value
Negative	3 (7.3%)	41 (67.2%)	0.0001
Positive	38 (92.7%)	20 (32.8%)	
Tumor stage	HER2 +2	HER2 +3	P-value
I	5 (12.2%)	7 (11.5%)	0.2
II	22 (53.7%)	39 (63.9%)	
III	14 (34.1%)	12 (19.7%)	
IV	0 (0.0%)	3 (4.9%)	
L.N. metastasis	HER2 +2	HER2 +3	P-value
Negative	16 (39.0%)	11 (18.0%)	0.023
Positive	25 (61.0%)	50 (82.0%)	
Tumor grades	HER2 +2	HER2 +3	P-value
I	7 (17.1%)	2 (3.3%)	0.0001
II	32 (78.0%)	33 (54.1%)	
III	2 (4.9%)	26 (42.6%)	
Histopathology	HER2 +2	HER2 +3	P-value
Invasive ductal carcinoma (NOS)	37 (90.2%)	60 (98.4%)	0.1
Invasive lobular carcinoma	4 (9.8%)	1 (1.6%)	

Table 3 illustrates the relationship between HER2 expression levels and two quantitative clinical parameters: tumor size and patient age.

Tumor Size: The mean tumor size among patients with HER2 +2 expression was 4.25 ± 1.985 cm, compared with 3.87 ± 2.170 cm in the HER2 +3 group. The difference between the two means was not statistically significant ($p = 0.3$). Although HER2 +3 tumors are generally associated with aggressive biological behavior, the absence of a significant difference in size suggests that tumor aggressiveness in HER2-overexpressing cancers may not always correlate with larger tumor dimensions, but rather with factors such as proliferation rate, invasion potential, and metastatic spread. These findings are consistent with previous studies reporting that HER2 status does not reliably predict tumor size at presentation, but rather

correlates with disease progression and recurrence risk.

Age Distribution: The mean age of patients with HER2 +2 expression was 53.80 ± 11.125 years, while those with HER2 +3 overexpression had a mean age of 49.87 ± 9.235 years, showing a borderline statistically significant difference ($p = 0.05$). This result indicates that HER2 overexpression tends to occur in relatively younger patients, which is in line with published data suggesting that younger women are more likely to present with HER2-positive and higher-grade tumors. This age-related distribution may reflect underlying genetic or hormonal differences influencing tumor biology in younger patients and highlights the importance of early detection strategies in this subgroup.

Table 3: Differences Mean of Tumor Size and Age According to HER 2 Status

Variable	HER2 Status	N	Mean \pm SD	P-value
Tumor Size (cm)	+2	41	4.25 ± 1.985	0.3
	+3	61	3.87 ± 2.170	
Age (years)	+2	41	53.80 ± 11.125	0.05
	+3	61	49.87 ± 9.235	

Figure 1: Representative Examples of Human Epidermal Growth Factor Receptor 2 (HER2) Immunohistochemistry (IHC) in Breast Cancer. (A) HER2 IHC Negative (0). (B) HER2 IHC Negative (1+). (C) HER2 IHC Equivocal (2+). (D) HER2 IHC Positive (3+).

Discussion

The present study assessed the diagnostic and histological significance of HER2 expression in breast carcinoma and its correlation with key clinicopathological features. The findings highlight the biological heterogeneity of breast cancer among Iraqi women and reaffirm the prognostic importance of HER2 as a marker of tumor aggressiveness. The mean age of patients was 51 ± 10 years, with most cases occurring in the fifth decade of life, consistent with findings from Mohammed DR et al. [14] and Aman NA et al. [15], who reported similar mean ages among Iraqi breast cancer patients. Globally, the median age at diagnosis varies between 48 and 55 years, with slightly younger onset observed in Middle Eastern populations [16]. This may reflect regional genetic, reproductive, and environmental risk factors. In the current study, 54.9% of cases were PR-positive, and 56.9% were ER-positive, which is in agreement with previous Iraqi studies reporting hormone receptor positivity between 50% and 60% [17,18]. The coexistence of hormone receptor positivity with HER2 overexpression in some cases supports the presence of the luminal B subtype, which is known for intermediate prognosis and partial response to hormonal therapy [19]. HER2 overexpression (+3) was detected in 59.8% of tumors, a higher rate than that reported by Aman NA et al. [15]

(44%) and Testa U et al. [20] (20–25%), but comparable to regional studies suggesting higher HER2 positivity in Middle Eastern women [21]. The predominance of HER2-positive disease in this cohort implies a biologically aggressive tumor profile, frequently linked to poor differentiation and early recurrence if untreated [22]. A significant inverse association was noted between HER2 expression and both ER and PR status ($p = 0.0001$), which is consistent with findings by Iqbal et al. [23] and Garrett JT et al. [24], who reported that HER2 amplification is often associated with hormone receptor–negative tumors, characterizing the HER2-enriched molecular subtype. This subgroup typically exhibits rapid proliferation, resistance to hormonal therapy, and a worse clinical outcome without HER2-targeted treatment [25]. A significant relationship was also identified between HER2 positivity and lymph node metastasis ($p = 0.023$), corroborating studies by Mohammed DR et al. [14] and Lyu C et al. [26], which emphasized the role of HER2 overexpression in promoting tumor invasiveness and metastatic potential. Additionally, a strong correlation was observed between HER2 overexpression and higher tumor grade ($p = 0.0001$), reinforcing the association between HER2 status and poor histologic differentiation [27]. Although no significant association was found between HER2 expression and tumor stage

($p = 0.2$), most patients presented with stage II–III disease, a finding consistent with delayed diagnosis and limited screening practices in Iraq. Similarly, no significant relationship was observed between HER2 and tumor size, indicating that HER2-driven aggressiveness is not necessarily reflected by tumor dimension, but rather by molecular activity and metastatic capability, as reported by Nash CE et al. [28]. The mean age of patients with HER2 +3 tumors was slightly lower than that of HER2 +2 cases (49.8 vs. 53.8 years, $p = 0.05$), consistent with the observation that younger women tend to develop HER2-positive tumors, as described by Bischoff A et al. [29].

Conclusion

Overall, these findings confirm that HER2 overexpression is significantly associated with high histologic grade, hormone receptor negativity, and lymph node metastasis, defining a subset of breast cancers with more aggressive clinical behavior but favorable response to targeted therapy.

References

- [1] Sung H, Ferlay J, Siegel RL, et al. Global Cancer Statistics 2020: GLOBOCAN Estimates of Incidence and Mortality Worldwide for 36 Cancers in 185 Countries. *CA Cancer J Clin.* 2021 May;71(3):209-249. doi: 10.3322/caac.21660. Epub 2021 Feb 4. PMID: 33538338.
- [2] Mahendralingam MJ, Kim H, McCloskey CW, et al. Mammary epithelial cells have lineage-rooted metabolic identities. *Nat Metab.* 2021 May;3(5):665-681. doi: 10.1038/s42255-021-00388-6. Epub 2021 May 20. PMID: 34031589.
- [3] Cherifi F, Da Silva A, Johnson A, et al. HELENA: HER2-Low as a predictive factor of response to Neoadjuvant chemotherapy in early breast cancer. *BMC Cancer.* 2022 Oct 20;22(1):1081. doi: 10.1186/s12885-022-10163-9. PMID: 36266623; PMCID: PMC9585737.
- [4] Liu S, Fang C, Zhong C, et al. Recent advances in pluripotent stem cell-derived cardiac organoids and heart-on-chip applications for studying anti-cancer drug-induced cardiotoxicity. *Cell Biol Toxicol.* 2023 Dec;39(6):2527-2549. doi: 10.1007/s10565-023-09835-4. Epub 2023 Oct 27. PMID: 37889357.
- [5] Iqbal N, Iqbal N. Human Epidermal Growth Factor Receptor 2 (HER2) in Cancers: Overexpression and Therapeutic Implications. *Mol Biol Int.* 2014;2014:852748. doi: 10.1155/2014/852748. Epub 2014 Sep 7. PMID: 25276427; PMCID: PMC4170925.
- [6] Yang Y, Tian Z, Guo R, Ren F. Nrf2 Inhibitor, Brusatol in Combination with Trastuzumab Exerts Synergistic Antitumor Activity in HER2-Positive Cancers by Inhibiting Nrf2/HO-1 and HER2-AKT/ERK1/2 Pathways. *Oxid Med Cell Longev.* 2020 Jul 19;2020:9867595. doi: 10.1155/2020/9867595. PMID: 32765809; PMCID: PMC7387975.
- [7] Moradi Y, Lee JSH, Armani AM. Detecting Disruption of HER2 Membrane Protein Organization in Cell Membranes with Nanoscale Precision. *ACS Sens.* 2024 Jan 26;9(1):52-61. doi: 10.1021/acssensors.3c01437. Epub 2023 Nov 13. PMID: 37955934; PMCID: PMC10825864.
- [8] Rakha EA, Ellis IO. Modern classification of breast cancer: should we stick with morphology or convert to molecular profile characteristics. *Adv Anat Pathol.* 2011 Jul;18(4):255-67. doi: 10.1097/PAP.0b013e318220f5d1. PMID: 21654357.
- [9] Ghosh R, Narasanna A, Wang SE, et al. Trastuzumab has preferential activity against breast cancers driven by HER2 homodimers. *Cancer Res.* 2011 Mar 1;71(5):1871-82. doi: 10.1158/0008-5472.CAN-10-1872. Epub 2011 Feb 15. PMID: 21324925; PMCID: PMC3221734.
- [10] Wolff AC, Hammond MEH, Allison KH, et al. Human Epidermal Growth Factor Receptor 2 Testing in Breast Cancer: American Society of Clinical Oncology/College of American Pathologists Clinical Practice Guideline Focused Update. *Arch Pathol Lab Med.* 2018 Nov;142(11):1364-1382. doi: 10.5858/arpa.2018-0902-SA. Epub 2018 May 30. PMID: 29846104.
- [11] Jumaah AS, Shaker RA, Al-Ali Z, et al. Immunohistochemical Breast Cancer Profiling Among Iraqi Women: Molecular Subtype Classification, Clinicopathology Associations, and Treatment-Decision Making Tools: A Cross-Sectional Study. *Health Sci Rep.* 2025 May 19;8(5):e70553. doi: 10.1002/hsr.2.70553. PMID: 40391262; PMCID: PMC12086652.
- [12] Mohanty SS. Correlation of expression of hormone and HER2 receptors with various clinicopathological prognostic parameters and with each other in malignant breast lesion. *Ann Diagn Pathol.* 2021 Feb;50:151659. doi: 10.1016/j.anndiagpath.2020.151659. Epub 2020 Nov 5. PMID: 33249360.
- [13] Wu SG, Wang J, Lian CL, et al. Evaluation of the 8th edition of the American joint committee on cancer's pathological staging system in prognosis assessment and treatment decision making for stage T1-2N1 breast cancer after mastectomy. *Breast.* 2020 Jun;51:2-10. doi: 10.1016/j.breast.2020.02.012. Epub 2020 Mar 3. PMID: 32172191; PMCID: PMC7375569.
- [14] Mohammed DR, Alwan NA, Hussein R. Immunohistochemical Assessment of Estrogen, Progesterone Receptors and HER2-neu Over Expression by Core Needle Biopsy in a Sample of Iraqi Breast Cancer Patients. *J. Contemp. Med. Sci. [Internet].* 2019 Aug. 26 [cited 2025 Nov. 1];5(4):214-7.
- [15] Aman NA, Doukoure B, Koffi KD, et al. HER2 overexpression and correlation with other significant clinicopathologic parameters in Ivorian breast cancer women. *BMC Clin Pathol.* 2019 Jan 17;19:1. doi:

10.1186/s12907-018-0081-4. PMID: 30675127; PMCID: PMC6335844.

[16] Bray F, Laversanne M, Sung H, et al. Global cancer statistics 2022: GLOBOCAN estimates of incidence and mortality worldwide for 36 cancers in 185 countries. *CA Cancer J Clin.* 2024 May-Jun;74(3):229-263. doi: 10.3322/caac.21834. Epub 2024 Apr 4. PMID: 38572751.

[17] Khalaf H, Mohammed A, Shukur S, et al. Breast cancer: age incidence, hormone receptor status and family history in Najaf, Iraq. *J Med Life.* 2022 Oct;15(10):1318-1321. doi: 10.25122/jml-2022-0296. PMID: 36420288; PMCID: PMC9675305.

[18] Al-Bedairy IH, Al-Faisal AHM, Al-Gazali HR, Al-Mudhafar H. Molecular subtypes by immunohistochemical for Iraqi women with breast cancer. *Iraqi J Biotechnol.* 2020 Apr;19(1):18–27.

[19] Gutierrez-Riquelme T, Karkossa I, Schubert K, et al. Proteomic analysis of extracellular vesicles derived from canine mammary tumour cell lines identifies protein signatures specific for disease state. *BMC Vet Res.* 2024 Oct 26;20(1):488. doi: 10.1186/s12917-024-04331-1. PMID: 39462388; PMCID: PMC11515202.

[20] Testa U, Castelli G, Pelosi E. Breast Cancer: A Molecularly Heterogenous Disease Needing Subtype-Specific Treatments. *Medical Sciences.* 2020; 8(1):18. doi: 10.3390/medsci8010018.

[21] Sengal AT, Haj-Mukhtar NS, Elhaj AM, et al. Immunohistochemistry defined subtypes of breast cancer in 678 Sudanese and Eritrean women; hospitals based case series. *BMC Cancer.* 2017 Dec 1;17(1):804. doi: 10.1186/s12885-017-3805-4. PMID: 29191181; PMCID: PMC5710067.

[22] Kok JPC, Haji Abdul Hamid MRW, Patnaik RS, Kok KYY. Fluorescence in situ hybridisation analysis of human epidermal growth factor receptor 2 status for breast cancer cases in Brunei Darussalam. *Cancer Rep (Hoboken).* 2020 Oct;3(5):e1249. doi: 10.1002/cnr2.1249. Epub 2020 Jun 8. PMID: 33085848; PMCID: PMC7941490.

[23] Iqbal N, Iqbal N. Human Epidermal Growth Factor Receptor 2 (HER2) in Cancers: Overexpression and Therapeutic Implications. *Mol Biol Int.* 2014;2014:852748. doi: 10.1155/2014/852748. Epub 2014 Sep 7. PMID: 25276427; PMCID: PMC4170925.

[24] Garrett JT, Sutton CR, Kuba MG, et al. Dual blockade of HER2 in HER2-overexpressing tumor cells does not completely eliminate HER3 function. *Clin Cancer Res.* 2013 Feb 1;19(3):610-9. doi: 10.1158/1078-0432.CCR-12-2024. Epub 2012 Dec 5. PMID: 23224399; PMCID: PMC3563762.

[25] Wolff AC, Somerfield MR, Dowsett M, et al. Human Epidermal Growth Factor Receptor 2 Testing in Breast Cancer: ASCO-College of American Pathologists Guideline Update. *J Clin Oncol.* 2023 Aug 1;41(22):3867-3872. doi: 10.1200/JCO.22.02864. Epub 2023 Jun 7. PMID: 37284804.

[26] Lyu C, Ye Y, Lensing MM, et al. Targeting Gi/o protein-coupled receptor signaling blocks HER2-induced breast cancer development and enhances HER2-targeted therapy. *JCI Insight.* 2021 Sep 22;6(18):e150532. doi: 10.1172/jci.insight.150532. PMID: 34343132; PMCID: PMC8492335.

[27] Pang SJ, Li CC, Shen Y, et al. Value of counting positive PHH3 cells in the diagnosis of uterine smooth muscle tumors. *Int J Clin Exp Pathol.* 2015 May 1;8(5):4418-26. PMID: 26191133; PMCID: PMC4503005.

[28] Nash CE, Mavria G, Baxter EW, et al. Development and characterisation of a 3D multi-cellular in vitro model of normal human breast: a tool for cancer initiation studies. *Oncotarget.* 2015 May 30;6(15):13731-41. doi: 10.18632/oncotarget.3803. PMID: 25915532; PMCID: PMC4537045.

[29] Bischoff A, Bayerlová M, Strotbek M, et al. A global microRNA screen identifies regulators of the ErbB receptor signaling network. *Cell Commun Signal.* 2015 Jan 29;13:5. doi: 10.1186/s12964-015-0084-z. PMID: 25630670; PMCID: PMC4314810.

